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FACTORS AFFECTING THE ADOPTION OF ELECTRONIC RECORD MANAGEMENT SYSTEM (ERMS) IN THE GOVERNMENT SECTOR

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Article Info	ABSTRACT
<p>Article history: Received: 22 Feb 2025 Revised: 4 March 2025 Accepted: 25 March 2025 Published: 1 April 2025</p> <p>Keywords: <i>System quality, Training, E-government, Electronic Records, Records Management, Electronic Records Management System (ERMS).</i></p> <p></p>	<p>An ERMS is a computer system with specialised functionality for managing electronic records that is created using existing records management principles and practices while taking into consideration the electronic format. It is an application designed to help organisations manage their existing electronic records more effectively. The Electronic Records Management System (ERMS) is one of the most significant parts of electronic record management. It was designed to monitor both physical and electronic forms, not just digital ones. This concept paper aims to identify the factors affecting the implementation of an Electronic Records Management System in the government sector. Based on the previous literature, the three primary factors examined are system quality, training, and e-government. Thus, the government sector should be aware of the factors that can influence the development of strategies and guidelines for employees to adopt ERMS and utilise it regularly in their everyday tasks.</p>

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INTRODUCTION

An electronic records management system (ERMS) is a computer system with specialised functions designed to manage electronic records in accordance with established records management principles and practices, while taking into account their electronic format. It is an application designed to improve the management of current electronic records in organisations. It was designed not just to maintain digital data, but also to monitor both physical and electronic records. This study was conducted to determine the factors influencing the installation of an Electronic Records Management System in the government sector. According to Mukred et al. (2021), organisational, technological, and environmental issues arose throughout implementing and using IT systems in Malaysia's public and private sectors, including higher education and health. According to Glyptis et al. (2020), developing the telecommunications infrastructure will be expensive when e-government is implemented. The goal of Malaysia's e-government development is to improve information flows and processes, as well as the speed, accuracy, and effectiveness of public service delivery. This will help with policy formulation, coordination, and enforcement (Liyana, Yadegaridehkordi, & Sulaiman, 2019). The first step in successfully adopting ERMS is thought to be accepting IT. An organisation must first decide which system to implement, facilitating system adoption through hands-on usage of the technology. It is, therefore vital to pinpoint the crucial success factors that will affect the implementation of ERMS within an organisation in any Malaysian government sector. To comprehend why ERMS has not been prioritised in underdeveloped nations, Waleed et al. (2020) claim that factors impacting ERMS adoption in an organisation have not been substantially explored or studied. Previous studies merely outlined the general aspects of such adoption, focusing on various contexts such as telecommunications, health, and education in poor nations (Mukred et al., 2021).

Managing electronic records in an organisation requires a good system so that staff can easily access data and records in the long term. Malak (2022) emphasises the need of records management best practices in ensuring legal and regulatory compliance. They help companies manage their records by organising, categorising, storing, and deleting them. Thus, in managing electronic records, the implementation of ERMS helps the organisation to fulfill those requirements. Electronic content and new technologies are considered a serious challenge to organisations maintaining a safe preservation and ease of access. That is why it is an urgent need to study the factor that influences the adoption of an ERMS. Therefore, this study aims to identify the three main factors why an organisation chooses ERMS to manage their records. The objective of this study is to investigate the relationships between key factors and the intention to implement an Electronic Records Management System (ERMS). The study's specific objectives are to determine the relationship between System Quality and the intention to implement ERMS, to determine the relationship between training and the intention to adopt ERMS, and to determine the relationship between e-government activities and the intention to implement ERMS. Similarly, the research aims to answer the following questions: What is the relationship between system quality and the intention to use ERMS? How does training affect the intention to implement ERMS? What is the relationship between E-Government and the intention to adopt ERMS?

LITERATURE REVIEW

In order to authenticate this research in producing and combining the concepts with the prior research or study, a large number of publications, books, and journals were studied.

System Quality

System design is a crucial impact, according to a study done by Patimo and Maribojoc (2021) at Northwest Samar State University in Calbayog City utilising ERMS. The user interface, input design, processing performance, database design, and output design of a proposed system must all be legitimate and acceptable. These allowed for the design and development of the ERMS to be improved and finished in preparation for a

successful system installation. A high system quality is the foundation of good record management. Hawash et al. (2020) cite the positive qualities of ERMS in respect to its operational features. Perceived ease of use was significantly influenced by system quality. Additionally, mobile learning is seen as being valuable when both the information delivered and the system's effectiveness are high.

The majority of users found the ERMS's functions to be speedy and dependable. Salleh, Abdullah, and Zakaria (2021) assessed how the adoption of an electronic health records system affected the performance of Malaysian healthcare providers and discovered that system quality is necessary to provide adequate IT infrastructure, system interoperability, alleviate perceived security concerns, and make ERMS systems compatible with the clinical tasks carried out by care providers. Other than that, record quality guarantees that an ERMS format that is standardised and user-friendly enables quick and minimal data entry for the care professionals to carry out prompt diagnosis and treatment without delay. Regarding service quality, it refers to the standard of technical support provided by ERMS system vendors and internal IT staff to gauge efficient use and clinical performance (Mukred et al., 2021).

Training

In addition, Zulkipli et al. (2021) emphasise the training as a functional necessity of ERMS. All staff and employees must receive training on how to operate the system correctly, how to scan and enter paper documents already in the system, and how to convert newly generated documents to electronic format. According to Hawash et al. (2020), users within the organisation should be given awareness and skills to raise their level of understanding and provide a good manner to foster favourable intents about adopting ERMS. Records managers must first prepare for change while deploying ERMS by developing a change management plan and assembling a change management team to lead the transition. This component is also influenced by change management (Shonhe & Grand, 2020).

Top management support is crucial to establishing their dedication to and compliance with the management departments in an organisation, as stated by Mukred et al. (2021). To improve compliance with handling electronic records as a record, employees' abilities must be evaluated and training provided to overcome any gaps. This can be accomplished by reviewing the electronic records creation and capture process, which can be noted in the manner in which activities are executed (Sheikh Abdul Mutalib, McLeod, & Moss, 2017). Additionally, training should be given so that users can personalise materials for their duties, add the full business task to the system, and satisfy their needs. The compilation and administration of accurate, reliable, usable records to support decision-making and business processes is essential for the establishment and promotion of the ERMS policy here are also project management factors that determine ERMS implementation.

E-Government

The conclusion showed by Ambira et al. (2019) is that Kenya's government ministries have large numbers of electronic records. The majority of the electronic records made or generated by government ministries are transactional records, including records that were born digital and records that were digitalized as a result of scanning manual records into digital formats. Ambira et al. (2019) further explained that the current analysis has concluded that Kenya has a substantial level of e-government penetration and is ready for improved delivery of e-based services. The paper asserts that there have been minimal attempts to link ERMS with e-government in Kenya, even though all of the ministries regarded ERMS as being crucial to the growth of e-government. The conclusions showed that Kenyan records management professionals have not done much to integrate electronic records into the overall e-government framework.

Yan and Huping (2020) stated that the degree to which the government facilitates successful information search, transactions, and communication between government and citizens, as well as how well public services offered by the government match user needs, can be used by users to describe the quality of e-government services. The quality of an e-government service is a culmination of all the elements and qualities that go into providing a specific public service. Better ERMS are foundational to good governance and high performance, according to Ukata and Wechie (2019), and they are a crucial component of e-government services. The primary forces behind various ERM strategies in e-government strategy are related to the main business of e-government. In an e-government plan, the entire life cycle control model is employed to manage electronic records. The goal of Vision 2020 is for Malaysia to become a developed country by the year 2020. In Malaysia context, the implementation of e-government began with the establishment of Multimedia Super Corridor (MSC) in 1997 in

which e-government was one of the seven flagships of the initiative (Sheikh Abdul Mutalib, McLeod, & Moss, 2017; Kaur, 2006). Malaysia's transition from paper-based to electronic records began with the establishment of the MSC in 1996, which marked the first step towards electronic government (Johare, 2001). Former Malaysian Prime Minister Tun Dr. Mahathir Mohammad's speech unveiling Vision 2020 inspired the creation of the MSC. The MSC was a government-sponsored effort aimed at promoting the growth of information and communication technology (ICT) in Malaysia (Hamsha,2012).

METHODOLOGY

Reviews of relevant literature are the main methodology in this study. The literature review has been done through document analysis from previous studies. This study employs a qualitative research design, specifically a conceptual analysis of the existing literature. Conceptual papers prioritise theoretical development and synthesis over actual data collection (Meredith, 1993). This study seeks to discover patterns, gaps, and emerging trends in the selected body of literature through a critical examination of existing work. The study collects secondary data via sourcing peer-reviewed journal articles, books, and conference papers on the research topic. To ensure a methodical approach, databases such as Google Scholar, Scopus, and Web of Science will be utilised. Keywords and Boolean operators will refine the search process, ensuring a comprehensive yet focused literature base (Kitchenham & Charters, 2007). A thematic analysis method is used to investigate reoccurring themes, concepts, and theoretical views in the literature (Braun and Clarke, 2006). To maintain rigour, the study employs a structured review method that includes triangulation through cross-referencing multiple sources. Reflexivity is maintained to reduce researcher bias, while peer debriefing is used to improve analytical dependability (Lincoln & Guba, 1985). Since this is a conceptual paper relying solely on secondary sources, no ethical approval is required. Ethical standards are maintained by properly crediting all cited works and avoiding falsification of original findings (Zupic & Čater, 2015).

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

In summary, ERMS is a vital instrument for managing electronic records. Over the last decade, it has become clear that an efficient ERMS is vital for effective electronic recordkeeping. ERMS is responding to the needs of its users, who rely on activities done throughout the e-records life cycle. The records management practitioner should be able to select a suitable records system to ensure that electronic records are managed properly. Data and findings were gathered from previously selected articles associated with the ERMS to assist in determining the suggestion. This study also focused on ERMS adoption and variables, and the findings can provide a more in-depth understanding of the government sector and other domains in terms of the aspects that must be addressed for successful system adoption. This study spurred greater research into the function of ERMS in decision-making, as well as the development of a proper framework for the adoption process.

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